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DEVELOPMENT OF MOTIVATION IN STUDENTS, STUDYING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN NON-LANGUAGE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

ANNOTATION

The article focuses on the fundamental problem of the development of motivation among students in non-linguistic universities that study basic and technical English as a foreign language. A significant place in the article is given to the huge role of the teacher in raising and strengthening motivation, which is the key to an effective educational process.

Keywords: motivation, effective ways of learning, motive, English, fundamental problem, student, technical English.

РАЗВИТИЕ МОТИВАЦИИ У СТУДЕНТОВ, ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ИНОСТРАННЫХ ЯЗЫКОВ В НЕЯЗЫКОВЫХ ВУЗАХ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена фундаментальной проблеме развития мотивации студентов неязыковых вузов, изучающих базовый и технический английский язык как иностранный. Значительное место в статье отведено огромной роли учителя в поднятии и укреплении мотивации, которая является залогом эффективного образовательного процесса.

Ключевые слова: мотивация, эффективные способы обучения, мотив, английский язык, фундаментальная проблема, студент, технический английский язык.

ТИЛГА ИХТИСОСЛААШМАГАН ОЛИЙ ЎҚУВ ЮРТЛАРИДАГИ ТАЛАБАЛАРГА ЧЕТ-ТИЛИНИ ЎРГАТИШДА МОТИВАЦИЯНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Мақола асосий ва техник инглиз тилини чет-тили сифатида ўрганаётган нолингвистик олий ўқув юртлари талабаларининг мотивациясини ривожлантиришнинг асосий муаммосига бағишланади. Мақолада самарали таълим жараёнининг калити бўлган мотивацияни ошириш ва мустаҳкамлашда ўқитувчининг улкан роли кўрсатилган.

Калит сўзлар: мотивация, ўрганишнинг самарали усуллари, мотив, инглиз тили, fundamental муаммо, талаба, техник инглиз тили.

The obvious relevance and importance of this problem, which is constantly faced by foreign language providers in secondary and higher educational institutions are confirmed by the results of a survey among students of different levels of language proficiency from the first for the third year. The purpose of the survey in the form of anonymous questionnaires were to identify, analyze and summarize the main factors affecting both external and internal motivation, as well as the causes of low motivations.

Particular attention is paid to the use of active teaching methods, such as role-playing games, debates that provide an opportunity to develop and improve business skills, communications and professionally oriented skills. Significant place in the article is devoted in that the huge role of the teacher in raising and strengthening motivation, which is the key effective educational process. The article provides various points of view on the problem of motivation of both native and foreign teachers and psychologists.

The most important significance of the article is that the author, relying on her own many years of experience of teaching students English gives useful recommendation in solving the problems of motivation, which may be of interest to teachers at schools and universities.

- *motivation factors;*
- *low and high motivation;*
- *internal and external motivation;*
- *active teaching methods;*
- *professionally-oriented training;*
- *development and improvement of motivation;*
- *professional competence*

The problem of formation and development motivation is one of the fundamental issues in psychology and pedagogy. The subject was investigated in many studies of both native and foreign researchers. However, there is no single point of view understanding the nature of motivation. Heckhausen H. distinguishes [1] between two types of motivation: internal (intrinsic) associated with internal needs and interests of human, and extrinsic motivation, relating to external circumstances Herzberg F [2] and Harmer J consider that motivation comes from the person himself and cannot be imposed from without it [3].

The opinion is partially shared by E.P. Ilyin, asserting that motivation is always provided internally, but at the same time it can depend on external factors, to be given external stimuli, and therefore it is difficult to distinguish the external and intrinsic motivations in pure form [4].

From his point of view, it would be more correct to talk about external and internal incentives, motivating process during which external factors transform into the internal. I.A. Zimniya sees motivation as “compulsory component of the structure of educational activity [5].

It can be internal or external towards activities but always remains an internal characteristic of personality as a subject of this activity. The challenge of arousing students’ interest to the language in non-linguistic universities has always stood in front of foreign teachers’ languages, since language is not generally prioritized in most non-core disciplines lines.

However, the situation is gradually changing. In an era of international connections and intercultural communication there are more opportunities to travel and even study abroad for young people. In addition, the desire to find promising work where very often knowledge of foreign languages is required, also makes students learn this subject deeper. All these factors have a significant effect on encouraging students to study foreign languages not only in everyday life, but also in professional oriented level.

What is the role of a teacher in modern changing conditions? At first glance, the task of drawing attention to your subject seems to be simplified by external motivation, which is provided by external factors, for example, the ability to communicate with foreign friends or desire to read a book, or watch a movie in the original.

Taking this fact into consideration, the teacher should concentrate not only on maintenance, but also on increasing existing motivation of students, which is the key to effective educational process. A survey was conducted in the form of anonymous questionnaire (questionnaire compiled by the author) among students 1-3 courses studying basic high and professionally oriented English in groups with different level training from Elementary to Upper Intermediate.

According to the survey of 247 students, 90% of the main motivating factor regardless of course and level of language proficiency is considered possibility of communication in English with foreign friends abroad; 86% students want to improve their knowledge; 77% believe that English is useful for them in future work; 72% polled people like English due to intrinsic motivation that prevails in Inter-mediate and Upper Intermediate; for 53% of students foreign language is essential to continue learning in magistracy or postgraduate studies, for 42% of students (mainly 1 year and Elementary and Low Intermediate - level groups) the main motivating factors are offset and passing the exams.

Thus, the survey showed a dominant factor of external motivation, and namely, the ability to use their knowledge and communication skills for communication both in a broad sense and in future professional activities. The survey results also confirm the theory of I.A. Zimniya, that distinguishes two types of motives which characterize the educational activity: motive of achievement and cognition motive [5].

The latter lies in new educational activities and is reflected in the desire of students to improve their knowledge, continue training in magistracy and graduate school. The motive for achievement is manifested in the implementation of professional ambitions and as a result, in raising social status, which is an important motive of most people. In addition, according to the survey, the motive changed over time at 61% students. So, in a secondary school, students treated a foreign language as one of the required subjects, and the rationale was getting positive assessment. However, university motivation significantly enhanced. Most students become aware of the need and importance of studying this subject, as it opens up new possibilities for self-improvement and further successful career. Therefore, 90% of students would like to continue to study the English language after 3 courses, and some, who are highly motivated, are ready to study it all life.

At the same time, 2.6% students (and not the weakest ones) would not like to learn English. Low motivation or lack of it is explained with various reasons:

1. English is not needed in future work;
2. Heavy workload by other items;
3. Sufficient knowledge;
4. preference is given to another foreign language.

It should be emphasized the role of a teacher in the development of student motivation. It is the teacher who needs to find out reasons for low motivation and try to create conditions for its appearance, and for motivated students to support and develop it. According to Lile W.T the lack of motivation or absence of it is the biggest obstacle for the teacher since it is a key for knowledge. He believes that any motivation is better than it lacks.

Peters R. also emphasizes the important role of motivation to succeed in educational activities. Often not very bright, but highly motivated students achieve better results than more capable, but unmotivated-students. What kind of student can be considered motivated? According to Gardner RC, motivation includes three components: effort + desire + positive attitude to achieve the goal (favored attitudes). Therefore, not every student making an effort is motivated. What contributes to the emergence and replay of motivation?

A.K. Markov pays attention to the main factors affecting formation of sustainable motivation to learning activities- content of educational material;

- organization of educational activities;
- collective forms of educational activity;
- assessment of educational activities;
- style of teacher in teaching

These ideas resonate in the works of foreign authors. According to Harris R. and Harmer J. students must put and understand the goals and objectives set in front of them. Many students are bad at performing tasks because they don't understand what they should do and why they should do it. Therefore, the absence of goals and misunderstanding can nullify the efforts and efforts of the teacher.

Besides the teacher must arrange academic work, providing students with material taking into account the level of training, professional qualities of students and orientation on their future specialty. An important condition undoubtedly is the creation of an auditorium of a special psychologically low tension (mild level of anxiety), trustful relations between teacher and students, providing emotionality of learning and supportive learning atmosphere areas are conducive to communication and affecting the level of academic activity of student activities.

Therefore, the teacher's identity is one of the most important factors in affecting motivation. The teacher must be caring, understanding, approachable and supportive, respecting the values and opinions of their students. Such teacher always manages to involve even most unmotivated students. We should not forget that encouraging and praise are strong motivating factors particularly for weak students.

It is well known that interest, curiosity, aspiration, the pursuit of knowledge stimulates any learning process. According to psychologists Coon D. and Mitterer JO internal stimulation intensifies when there is a desire to learn something new regardless from external motivating factors [9].

Students just get satisfied from educational activities and demonstrate great creativity when they are internally motivated. This view is given by Lile W. T saying that "internally motivated student studies because he wants to learn". On the other hand, he does not deny a positive role of external motivation, especially when there is little or no internal motivation. He believes that internally inspired students also need external motivation. If students are not encouraged for their efforts, internal motive will begin to decline.

The role of external motivation as an encouragement (for example, obtaining a certificate, exempting from an exam, etc.) is obvious. However, Malone T.W and Lepper MR consider that the quality of the work performed has a greater impact on inside factors: challenge: the desire to achieve, set goal and thereby increase your self-esteem; curiosity: aspiration to learn something new;

- cooperation and competition within the team;
- recognition: success of each is recognized by the team.

It is the teacher who must support such student aspirations through reward method: high appreciation of students even if their results have not yet reached the actual learning objectives, tact, kindness. The teacher's approval help students feel confident in their own strength and achieve their goals.

In this regard, making mistakes appears as another obstacle of the learning procedure. At the initial stage of learning when skills are formed with the use of language material in speech, error correction is necessary but in the form of hints. However, when conducting discussions, presentations, role playing games, that is, during the practice of communication when students reach enough high-level error correction is virtually eliminated. Correction is possible if a mistake makes understanding difficult or distort the meaning of utterance, that is, destroys the act of communication.

"Nothing can reduce enthusiasm and zeal, as permanent correction of errors", which can work out sustainable language barrier due to fear of making a mistake, and it will be much harder for the teacher to get students to be free in communication. Therefore, it is a good idea to evaluate students' results constantly and praise them even for modest successes, as encouragement is a necessary element in learning process. Intrinsic motivation, as already noted, depends on the teacher to a large extent: his personality, professional competence and ability call or maintain interest in his subject. In this case, the teacher should be oriented to the level and needs of students. First of all, it is necessary to follow the principle of homogeneity in terms of language level while the forming of training groups.

If a student is in a group, which is not corresponding to his level, it also may adversely affect his motivation. A weak student in a strong group will be constantly in a state of tension, and a strong student in a weak group may lose interest without seeing progress in his knowledge or even feeling a decline in his level. That is why testing in the form of conversation is important. It is more objective criterion in the assessment of language proficiency as opposed to written tests.

Getting to know the group at the beginning of the semester, it is a good idea to have an analysis of these needs so-called “needs analysis” and make a plan as part of the curriculum taking them into account. In other words, the principle of a flexible approach should lie at the heart of views. For instance, if students want more grammar, listening, conversation, etc., the teacher should take into account their wishes.

The survey also showed that Active Learning Methods (AMO) helps to increase the level of motivation. Given the communicative approach in learning of foreign languages using AMO is difficult to overestimate. Active learning methods include presentations, debates, training “brainstorming”, business games in the form of interviews, negotiations, gatherings telephone conversations, etc.

In basis of all these activities the principles of communicative directivity can be seen: students have the opportunity to use received professional competence in the main course in situations of business communication. Acquired knowledge of foreign language in the classroom must have a practical way outside the university. Otherwise, according to the survey, motivation even in strong students can decline if they are not be able to use their knowledge in real life situations, which means the process of training will not be effective enough. Role playing in preparation of future professionals is a unique form of simulation. Role-playing game is extremely an effective form of speech and mental activity aimed to solve a problem or task with which a future specialist may face in real life.

Consequently, problems or situations proposed for discussion should be professionally oriented, they should be “a way of motivation of speech activity” For this you need to create a motive for communication, that is, “a combination of such circumstances, which completely predetermine a turn of speech activity, that is, prompt it, determine its content and language design”.

For example, students may conduct job interviewing (job interview). They also can discuss personal ways of advertising and promotion, make a presentation of either product or service, etc. In the basis of any form of game lies the method of discussions, that give students ability to show their communicative skills, ability to express and argue own their point of view, agree or disagree with others, persuade their interlocutor using appropriate speech habits and language means of expression. It is in the role-play games that the skills of the community are improved in which students can manifest high level of communicative skills in the form of dialogue or polylogue (when, for example, role-playing is carried out in the form of a meeting).

Role play gives students a “sense of usefulness of what they are doing, which is powerful factor influencing the strengthening of motivation in language learning. It leads to activation of new involvement of students in the process of training.

Debate is another activity which attracts students since it gives students an opportunity to make them think over the problems and therefore it is the powerful factor of motivation. Participation in discussion clubs, university conferences, attending in lectures of foreign experts in foreign languages, participating in international projects and seminars, as well as going abroad for traineeship give students huge opportunities to realize their potential and improve their language skills. It is obvious that a strong stimulating factor in our time is various projects in the field of intercultural communication that based on new information technology. Integrated advanced educational technology leads to the need to look for new forms of teaching methods in educational process other than traditional ones (for example, participation in a videoconference lectures, seminars, lectures, read by native speakers), but also new forms of cooperation between teachers and students both within the walls of University and with their foreign colleagues.

The role of the teacher is changing: he ceases to be the only source of knowledge for students and rather becomes an assistant in obtaining information and partner in communication, ensure students linguistic and psychological support. Thus, the problem of development and increasing student motivation, learning foreign languages in non-profile universities, remains relevant. Teaching a foreign language certainly should be professionally oriented. It must be directly related to the future professional activities of students, therefore, attracting students to active participation in various projects, both in national and international, is an integral part of education process. It is again confirmed that the possibility of live communication in a foreign language is an essential motivation factor.

Finally, the role of the teacher in the development of an internal motivation is crucial. The degree of motivation in students depends on some issues such as, how the teacher builds a relationship with students, how he organizes the educational process, what kind of teaching methods he applies, how professional and interesting he is as a person.

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

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